

Table S1. The information of samples and Illumina RNA-Sequencing

Sample name	Raw reads	Clean reads	Clean bases	Q20 (%)	Q30 (%)	GC content (%)
XY_F_1_1	20205541	20159034	3.02G	98.69	96.17	46.82
XY_F_1_2	20205541	20159034	3.02G	97.33	93.35	46.87
XY_F_2_1	20305824	20279856	3.04G	98.86	96.53	47.25
XY_F_2_2	20305824	20279856	3.04G	97.52	93.7	47.29
XY_F_3_1	20385861	20337489	3.05G	98.78	96.36	47.03
XY_F_3_2	20385861	20337489	3.05G	97.31	93.24	47.06
XY_M_1_1	20329458	20307962	3.05G	98.86	96.56	46.11
XY_M_1_2	20329458	20307962	3.05G	97.41	93.48	46.14
XY_M_2_1	20320522	20304767	3.05G	98.88	96.55	48.04
XY_M_2_2	20320522	20304767	3.05G	97.63	93.95	48.08
XY_M_3_1	20285589	20238259	3.04G	98.78	96.34	47.7
XY_M_3_2	20285589	20238259	3.04G	97.49	93.63	47.73
XX_F_1_1	20357827	20329473	3.05G	98.91	96.66	47.82
XX_F_1_2	20357827	20329473	3.05G	97.28	93.2	47.85
XX_F_2_1	20247406	20224214	3.03G	98.92	96.67	47.36
XX_F_2_2	20247406	20224214	3.03G	97.21	93	47.4
XX_F_3_1	20365322	20334956	3.05G	98.89	96.61	47.55
XX_F_3_2	20365322	20334956	3.05G	97.09	92.75	47.59
YY_M_1_1	20188204	20176091	3.03G	99.1	97	46.09
YY_M_1_2	20188204	20176091	3.03G	96.99	91.62	46.17
YY_M_2_1	20081983	20068916	3.01G	99.11	97.02	46.27
YY_M_2_2	20081983	20068916	3.01G	96.85	91.26	46.36
YY_M_3_1	20392028	20379679	3.06G	99.13	97.07	46.41
YY_M_3_2	20392028	20379679	3.06G	96.94	91.47	46.46

Table S2. The comparison of clean reads with the reference genome

Sample name	Total reads	Total mapped	Multiple mapped	Uniquely mapped	Read_1	Read_2	Non_splice reads	Splice reads
XY_F_1	40318068	36622087 (90.83%)	1167097 (2.89%)	35454990 (87.94%)	17823526 (44.21%)	17631464 (43.73%)	20215995 (50.14%)	15238995 (37.8%)
XY_F_2	40559712	37206251 (91.73%)	1196139 (2.95%)	36010112 (88.78%)	18062289 (44.53%)	17947823 (44.25%)	19899958 (49.06%)	16110154 (39.72%)
XY_F_3	40674978	37354005 (91.84%)	1154579 (2.84%)	36199426 (89%)	18193206 (44.73%)	18006220 (44.27%)	20315268 (49.95%)	15884158 (39.05%)
XY_M_1	40615924	37740799 (92.92%)	1300603 (3.2%)	36440196 (89.72%)	18283548 (45.02%)	18156648 (44.7%)	21553646 (53.07%)	14886550 (36.65%)
XY_M_2	40609534	37629499 (92.66%)	1582730 (3.9%)	36046769 (88.76%)	18079443 (44.52%)	17967326 (44.24%)	18290285 (45.04%)	17756484 (43.72%)
XY_M_3	40476518	37283953 (92.11%)	1442337 (3.56%)	35841616 (88.55%)	18011857 (44.5%)	17829759 (44.05%)	19002123 (46.95%)	16839493 (41.6%)
XX_F_1	40658946	37809760 (92.99%)	1443924 (3.55%)	36365836 (89.44%)	18243507 (44.87%)	18122329 (44.57%)	17622709 (43.34%)	18743127 (46.1%)
XX_F_2	40448428	37918897 (93.75%)	1260537 (3.12%)	36658360 (90.63%)	18396189 (45.48%)	18262171 (45.15%)	18311904 (45.27%)	18346456 (45.36%)
XX_F_3	40669912	38100795 (93.68%)	1256642 (3.09%)	36844153 (90.59%)	18485535 (45.45%)	18358618 (45.14%)	18480772 (45.44%)	18363381 (45.15%)
YY_M_1	40352182	37318451 (92.48%)	1297142 (3.21%)	36021309 (89.27%)	18000578 (44.61%)	18020731 (44.66%)	21148362 (52.41%)	14872947 (36.86%)
YY_M_2	40137832	37282027 (92.89%)	1245154 (3.1%)	36036873 (89.78%)	18007234 (44.86%)	18029639 (44.92%)	20763346 (51.73%)	15273527 (38.05%)
YY_M_3	40759358	37935271 (93.07%)	1376891 (3.38%)	36558380 (89.69%)	18268641 (44.82%)	18289739 (44.87%)	21230422 (52.09%)	15327958 (37.61%)

XX_F vs XY_M

XX_F vs YY_M

XY_F vs XX_F

XY_F vs XY_M

XY_F vs YY_M

YY_M vs XY_M

Statistics of Pathway Enrichment

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